

Revisiting biosecurity decisions with hindsight: estimating the realised economic value of a historic medfly eradication

Supplementary Note

Data sources

We drew on a variety of historical data. Table S1 summarises the data sources for yearly data.

Key data sources are the New Zealand Official Yearbooks

(<https://www.stats.govt.nz/indicators-and-snapshots/digitised-collections/yearbook-collection-18932012/>), published most years from 1892 to 2010, and the Statistics New Zealand Infoshare website (<https://infoshare.stats.govt.nz/>) for more recent time series.

We performed various analyses based on a division of New Zealand (NZ) into “standardized districts”. Finding a subdivision with a suitable granularity that is relatively stable over the study period 1907–2020 was not straightforward. We chose to use cadastral land districts for this purpose. Each of these roughly corresponds to district orchard area data from the Official Yearbooks covering 1907–1971, although there have been several changes to the land districts, mostly reflecting subdivisions of larger North Island districts into smaller ones as New Zealand grew. These data were combined into a collection of “standardized” districts for the North Island (“Auckland”, “Hawke’s Bay”, “Gisborne” (from 1923), “Taranaki”, “Wellington”) and the South Island (“Marlborough”, “Nelson”, “Westland”, “Canterbury”, “Otago”, “Southland”). Our district “Auckland” includes the regions historically known under a variety of names (“Auckland”, “North Auckland”, “Central Auckland”, “South Auckland” and “Bay of Plenty”). See Fig. 1 for a map of New Zealand showing our standardized land districts.

Data from the Agricultural Production Survey were reported at a different, finer level (regional councils, also called territorial authorities). Territorial authorities are a division of New Zealand into 67–74 cities and districts, with some changes occurring over the study period. Geospatial analysis was used to develop a mapping from the territorial authorities to land districts and required geospatial data for the coastlines (<https://data.linz.govt.nz/layer/51153-nz-coastlines-and-islands-polygons-topo-150k/>), land districts (<https://data.linz.govt.nz/layer/50785-nz-land-districts/>), and territorial authorities for the survey years 2002 (<https://datafinder.stats.govt.nz/layer/25737-territorial-authority-2001/>), 2007 (<https://datafinder.stats.govt.nz/layer/25736-territorial-authority-2006/>), 2012 and 2017 (<https://datafinder.stats.govt.nz/layer/27778-territorial-authority-2017-generalised-version/>).

Table S1. Summary of sources for yearly data. All internet URLs were checked and validated on 26 June 2025.

Data (yearly)	Coverage	Source
New Zealand orchard area	1906–1981 with gaps 1982–2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table AGR001AA
Orchard area by fruit	1968–1981 with gaps 1982–2020 with gaps	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table AGR001AA
Orchard area by land district	1907–1971 with gaps 2002 2007 2012 2017	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand (2002) Statistics New Zealand (2007) Statistics New Zealand (2012) Statistics New Zealand agricultural production statistics June 2017
Apple production volume	1924–1981 with gaps	New Zealand Official Yearbooks
Apple production volume with yield	1992–1998 with gaps 1995, 1996, 1999–2020 with gaps	Fresh Facts (1999–2021) United Fresh: Fresh Facts (2013–2023)
Apple exports by volume (apples & pears)	1910–1924	New Zealand Official Yearbooks
Apple exports by volume (apples only)	1925–1963 1964–2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table EXP003AA
Apple exports by value (apples & pears)	1910–1928	New Zealand Official Yearbooks
Apple exports by value (apples only)	1929–1984 1985–2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table EXP006AA
Kiwifruit production volume	1956–1990 with gaps	New Zealand Official Yearbooks
Kiwifruit partial production with yield	1990–1993 1991–2019 2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks United Fresh: Fresh Facts (2013–2023) Zespri Group Ltd. Annual Report 2020/21
Kiwifruit exports by volume	1968, 1973–1984 1985–2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table EXP003AA
Kiwifruit exports by value	1975–1984 1985–2020	New Zealand Official Yearbooks Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table EXP006AA
Distributions of NZ apple exports by country	1964–2020	United Nations Statistics Division COMTRADE database
Distributions of NZ kiwifruit exports by country	1990–1995 1996–2020	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations FAOSTAT database United Nations Statistics Division COMTRADE database
NZ Consumer Price Index (CPI; second quarter)	1907–1925 1925–2020	Reserve Bank of New Zealand inflation calculator Statistics New Zealand Infoshare Table CPI009AA
NZ Gross Domestic Product (GDP; NZD)	1960–2022	The World Bank CPI all groups for New Zealand (Series NY.GDP.MKTP.CN)

Data analysis

Our basic approach to data preparation was to develop three families of complete time series over the years 1907– 2020 for apples and kiwifruit separately: (1) orchard area by land district, (2) NZ fruit production volumes and (3) fruit volume available for export. We could then combine these to approximate exportable fruit from land districts, for example. Separately we used country-specific data to determine the yearly distribution of apple and kiwifruit exports to individual countries. Combining the data allowed us to restrict production or export markets for fruit, allowing us to develop our alternative scenarios.

The analysis used Excel (Microsoft Corporation 2022) and R (R Core Team 2022). Linear regression used the `lm` command in R. Non-linear regression used the `nls` command in R. Interpolation used the `imputeTS` package (Moritz & Bartz-Beielstein 2017) in R unless otherwise mentioned. Iterative proportional fitting (i.e., “raking”) used the `mipfp` package (Barthélemy & Suesse, 2018). Spatial analysis used QGIS 200 software (QGIS Development Team 2022). For historical data, areas were converted to hectares (1 ha = 2.47105 acres), NZ currencies were converted to New Zealand dollars (NZ\$2 = 1 NZ pound), and fruit volumes were converted to metric units (kg or tonnes).

Orchard area

Orchard area time series must satisfy two relevant conditions. First, in any year, a breakdown of orchard area by fruit must give the NZ total orchard area. Although we only considered apples and kiwifruit here, to take full advantage of available data we considered all orchard fruits when data were available, then focused on apples and kiwifruit as appropriate. Second, a breakdown of orchard area by land district must give the NZ total orchard area.

To start, gaps in the yearly orchard area by fruit breakdown were filled using Stineman interpolation (Moritz & Bartz-Beielstein 2017, Stineman 1980) or zeros as appropriate (e.g., years before the production of newer fruits) to provide coverage for the years 1968 and 1973–2020. New Zealand total orchard area necessarily agreed with the area fruit breakdown data over 1968–2020, where that was available. This included the period 1976–2020 during which the national total time series was complete. Gaps in the total orchard area within the period 1907–1975 were filled by Stineman interpolation, yielding a complete time series of NZ total orchard area for 1907–2020.

For the orchard area by district breakdown, we could either work with the district areas (which must sum to the national total in each year), or the distribution of the national total (which must sum to one in each year). We used either approach depending on convenience. Orchard areas from the Agricultural Production Survey (2002, 2007, 2012, 2017) were provided as breakdowns of fruit by territorial authority. For each year of the Survey, geospatial analysis was used to identify each territorial authority with one of our standardized land districts. Where a territorial authority was split across land districts, the one with the largest fraction was used. This split had no bearing where we worked with a coarser North Island / South Island split, for which the territorial authorities were not split.

To develop a complete yearly breakdown of orchard area by district, different approaches were used for 1907–1963 (“pre-1963”) and 1963–2020 (“post-1963”). The year 1963 is not special from a data point of view but does reflect approximately when geopolitical forces (especially UK’s membership into the European Economic Community) were becoming more relevant for fresh fruit exports. Complete data for the pre-1963 period were achieved using a modelling approach, based on two steps. In the first step, the time series for each district was considered separately. Linear interpolation was used for three districts that posed fewer difficulties. For the other districts, non-linear regression was used to model each time series, controlling for external factors such as World Wars I and II, and allowing for concavity. These models were used to produce estimates in years of missing values. However, this approach need not give

yearly totals that agree with the NZ total orchard area. We accomplished this in a second step, in which any excess or deficit with respect to the national total was corrected with reference to complete data in neighbouring years.

Total orchard area by land district (1907-1963)

Gaps in the Auckland, Hawke's Bay and Gisborne time series were filled with simple linear interpolation. This avoid curvature-related overshoots from Stineman interpolation that are troublesome when normalizing back to the NZ national totals. Gisborne data started in 1923.

For the remaining districts, a non-linear regression was fitted to the data using the following model formula.

Taranaki:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ (b0+b1*x)*I(x>=1908 & x<=1911) + (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1920 &
x<=1927)+ (b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1928 & x<=1960) + (b6+b7*x)*I(x>=1960)
+(c0+c1*x)*WW1+ (d0)*WW2+ p0*exp(p1*(x-1911)^2)*I(x<=1930) ")
```

Wellington:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ (b0+b1*x)*I(x>=1908 & x<=1910) + (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1912 &
x<=1920)+ d*WW2+ p0*exp(p1*(x-1911)^2) + (b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1946 & x<=1960) +
(b6+b7*x)*I(x>=1960) ")
```

Marlborough:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+(b0+b1*x)*I(x<=1916)+ (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1920 & x<=1930)+
(b8+b9*x)*I(x>=1930 & x<=1946)+ p0*exp(p1*(x-1917)^2)*I(x<=1927) +
(b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1946 & x<=1955) + (b6+b7*x)*I(x>=1955) ")
```

Nelson:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ b6*I(x<=1907) + (b0+b1*x)*I(x>=1908 & x<=1917) +
(b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1920 & x<=1930)+ p0*exp(p1*(x-1919)^2)*I(x>=1909 & x<=1930)
+p3*(x-1936)*I(x>=1937&x<=1944) + (b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1945) ")
```

Westland:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ (b0+b1*x)*I(x<=1910) + (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1916 & x<=1930)+
(b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1930 & x<=1956)+ p0*exp(p1*(x-1911)^2) ")
```

Canterbury:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+(b0+b1*x)*I(x<=1911)+(b3+b4*x)*I(x>=1911 & x<=1929) +
(b5+b6*x)*I(x>=1930 & x<=1936) + (b10+b11*x)*I(x>=1937 & x<=1952)+
(b7+b8*x)*I(x>=1956) + b9*I(x>=1953 & x<=1955) +(c0+c1*x)*WW1+d*WW2 ")
```

Otago:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ (b00+b01*x)* I(x<=1909) + (b0+b1*x)*I(x<=1917)+
p0*exp(p1*(x-1918)^2)*I(x<=1930) + (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1919 & x<=1947) +
(b4+b5*x)*I(x>=1947 & x<=1959) + + (b6+b7*x)*I(x>=1960) ")
```

Southland:

```
f1a<- as.formula("y~a+ (b0+b1*x)*I(x<=1910) + (b2+b3*x)*I(x>=1920 & x<=1946)+  
  (c0+c1*x)*WW1+ d*WW2+ p0*I(x<=1920)*exp(p1*(x-1911)^2)")
```

The recreated time series are shown in Fig. S2.

Figure S2. Interpolated total orchard area by land district (1907-1963) for remaining districts. Black dots show historical data, red circles show model fit for years with historical data, and green dots show model-interpolated values. (Figure continues on the next three pages).

Figure S2 continued. (Figure continues on the next two pages).

Figure S2 continued. (Figure continues on the next page).

Figure S2 continued.

Orchard area by crop and land district (1964-2020)

From the post-1963 data, we built a more complete view. A total of 18 fruits were considered: apples, pears, apricots, cherries, nectarines, peaches, plums, grapefruit, lemons, mandarins, oranges (sweet), tangelos, kiwifruit, passionfruit, tamarillos, avocados (from 1978), feijoas (from 1978) and persimmons (from 1990). These were based on the 1968 fruit areas provided in the 1975 Official Yearbook, with the last three fruits added later. Distributions $P_{t,i,j}$ for each fruit i in $\{1,2,\dots,18\}$ across land districts j in $\{1,2,\dots,11\}$ could be found for the following years t : 1968 by raking using district and fruit marginal totals, 1994 by raking using a partial district orchard area by fruit breakdown (SriRamaratnam 2006), and the years $\{2002, 2007, 2012$ and $2017\}$ using the Agricultural Production Survey data of the appropriate year. These provided “knots” for each fruit. We found distributions for years between knots using convex combinations. That is, for knots at time t_0 and t_1 and years t in $\{t_0 + 1, \dots, t_1 - 1\}$, we used $P_{t,i,j} = \alpha_t P_{t_0,i,j} + (1 - \alpha_t) P_{t_1,i,j}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 18, j = 1, \dots, 11$, where $\alpha_t = (t_1 - t)/(t_1 - t_0)$. Note that as t gets closer to t_1 , α gets closer to 0 and the contributions of $P_{t_0,i,j}$ and $P_{t_1,i,j}$ go down and up, respectively. To extrapolate 2018-2020, we used the area fruit distributions from 2017. For newer fruits, we used the 1994 distribution for avocados and feijoas (1978–1994) and persimmons (1990–1994). Then, for each fruit, the total fruit orchard area $A_{t,i}$ was known for each year t in $\{1968, 1973, \dots, 2020\}$. We created the yearly district orchard areas $A_{t,i,j}$ for those years by distributing the total fruit orchard area according to $A_{t,i,j} = P_{t,i,j} A_{t,i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 18, j = 1, \dots, 11$.

Orchard area totals by district for 1965 and 1972 were each created by averaging the orchard areas from the years immediately before and after. We did not find complete distributions $P_{t,i,j}$ for years before 1968 as we were only focussed on apples and kiwifruit, there is no complete data for all 18 fruits in that time, and modelling the complete distributions for all fruits in that period was beyond the scope of this project. We also did not find $P_{t,i,j}$ for 1969–1972 as we did not have the total fruit orchard areas $A_{t,i}$ for those years. Interpolation specific to apples and kiwifruit was then performed, as described next.

Finally, breakdowns of yearly apple orchard area by district and kiwifruit orchard area by district were obtained. Apple orchard area for each district was obtained using a modelling approach for the fraction of district orchard area devoted to the fruit (1907–1967), Stineman interpolation of apple orchard area (1969–1972) or the district orchard area by fruit breakdowns obtained above (1968, 1973–2020). The modelling approach recognised the fraction of area devoted to apples varies between districts, was high in 1907, and had changed by 1968. It also distinguished between linear trends and “bubbles” (rapid increase then decrease in area)

before 1945, which were driven more by apples as the predominant commercial export fruit. Kiwifruit orchard area was handled similarly, although the modelling approach covers 1945–1967, and approximates the start of kiwifruit production with a linear interpolation between 0 in 1945 and the district’s 1968 fraction of orchard area devoted to kiwifruit. Production before 1945 was negligible and assumed to be zero.

Apple orchard area by land district

Apple orchard area for each district was obtained using a modelling approach for the fraction of district orchard area devoted to the fruit (1907—1967), Stineman interpolation of apple orchard area (1969—1972) or the district orchard area by fruit distributions obtained for knots {1968, 1994, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017} and between them in the period 1973—2020 by convex combinations. Note that the fraction of a district’s orchard area devoted to apples in 1968, a key data point for these models, was obtained by “raking” from the marginal totals for fruits and districts.

For Auckland and Hawke’s Bay the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In step one a fraction of district orchard area $p_t, t = 1907, \dots, 1968$ was found by linear interpolation between 95% in 1907 and the district’s 1968 proportion of total orchard area dedicated to apples (17.3% for Auckland, 70.2% for Hawke’s Bay). This was then used to find the yearly apple area for the district as $p_t A_t, t = 1907, \dots, 1968$ where $A_t, t = 1907, \dots, 1968$ is the district’s total orchard area.

For Gisborne, apple orchard area was found in the same way, noting that the relevant period here was 1923—1967 and that 44.0% of Gisborne orchard area was devoted to apples in 1968.

For Taranaki, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In 1968, 0% of Taranaki orchard area was devoted to apples. In step one a linear trend was fitted to the district’s orchard area, for the period 1930—1960, and then extrapolated to the entire 1907–1967 period. This represented a baseline trend for other fruit types in the district. The apple area was formed as 95% of the area over the linear trend. In particular, this attributed most of the orchard area in the 1907—1930 “bubble” to apples when they were the dominant fruit.

For Wellington, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In 1968, 59.9% of Wellington orchard area was devoted to apples. In step one a linear trend was fitted to the district’s orchard area, for the period 1930—1960, and then extrapolated to the entire 1907–1967 period. This represented a baseline trend. The yearly apple area was formed as 59.9% of the trend value plus 95% of the amount above the trend in each year. This approach

allowed for an overall decline in orchard area and attributed most of the orchard area in the 1907—1920 “bubble” to apples when they were the dominant fruit.

For Marlborough, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In 1968, 56.2% of Marlborough orchard area was devoted to apples. In step one a linear trend was fitted to the district’s orchard area, for the period {1902—1908, 1930—1968} and then extrapolated to the entire 1907-1967 period. This represented a baseline trend. The yearly apple area was formed as 56.2% of the trend value, plus 95% of the amount above the trend in each year in 1907—1945. This approach allowed for an overall increase in orchard area and attributed most of the orchard area above that in 1907—1945, including the 1907—1930 “bubble”, to apples when they were the dominant fruit.

For Nelson, the model for the apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In 1968, 82.8% of Nelson orchard area was devoted to apples. In step one a linear trend was fitted to the district’s orchard area, for the period {1902—1908, 1930—1968} and then extrapolated to the entire 1907-1967 period. This represented a baseline trend. The yearly apple area was formed as 82.8% of the trend value, plus 95% of the amount above the trend in each year in 1907—1945. This approach allowed for an overall increase in orchard area and attributed most of the orchard area above that in 1907—1945, including the 1907—1930 “bubble”, to apples when they were the dominant fruit.

For Westland, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in one step. In 1968, 0% of Westland orchard area was devoted to apples, and orchard area in the district was small in general. The yearly apple area was taken to be 95% of the district’s orchard area. In particular, this attributed most of the area in the 1907—1930 “bubble” to apples, when they were the dominant fruit.

For Canterbury, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in one step. In 1968, 59.9% of Canterbury orchard area was devoted to apples. The yearly apple area was taken to be 59.9% of the district’s orchard area. In particular, this allowed for declining orchard area, and attributed most of the area in the 1907—1940 period to apples, when they were the dominant fruit.

For Otago, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in two steps. In 1968, 23.7% of Nelson orchard area was devoted to apples. In step one a linear trend was fitted to the district’s orchard area, for the period {1902—1908, 1930—1968} and then extrapolated to the entire 1907—1967 period. This represented a baseline trend. The yearly apple area was formed as 23.7% of the trend value, plus 95% of the amount above the trend in each year in 1907—

1945. This approach allowed for an overall trend in orchard area and attributed most of the orchard area above that in 1907—1945 to apples when they were the dominant fruit.

For Southland, the model for apple orchard area (1907—1967) was formed in one step. In 1968, 0% of Westland orchard area was devoted to apples and orchard area in the district is small in general. The yearly apple area was taken to be 95% of the district’s orchard area. In particular, this attributed most of the area in the 1908—1920 “bubble” to apples, when they were the dominant fruit.

Resulting time series for apple orchard area are shown in Fig. S3.

We found various other comments as anecdotal evidence regarding the size of apple orchard areas in 1907—1968. Although they were not used directly in the model, their agreement with modelled areas validates our results (Table S2).

Table S2. Other evidence for apple orchard areas (1907—1968)

Year	Comment	Source	Model Results
1945	apples comprise over half of total orchard area	1946 Official Yearbook	apples are 59% of total orchard area
1956	apples comprise over half of total orchard area	1957 Official Yearbook	apples are 54% of total orchard area
1957	apples comprise over half of total orchard area	1958 Official Yearbook	apples are 54% of total orchard area
1962	apples & pears are primarily grown in Nelson & Hawke's Bay	1963 Official Yearbook	Nelson + Hawke's Bay comprises 66% of apple orchard area 2nd place is 2.56 x 3rd place
~1967	Otago has about 10% of NZ apple trees	Monigatti (1966, p. 67)	Otago has 9% of apple orchard area

Figure S3. Reconstructed time series for apple orchard area by district. (Figure continues on the next three pages).

Figure S3 continued. (Figure continues on the next two pages).

Figure S3 continued. (Figure continues on the next page).

Figure S3 continued.

Kiwifruit orchard area by land district

Kiwifruit orchard area for each district was obtained using a modelling approach for 1945—1967, Stineman interpolation of kiwifruit orchard area (1969—1972) or the district orchard area by fruit distributions obtained for knots {1968, 1994, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017} and between them in the period 1973—2020 by convex combinations. The modelling approach used a linear interpolation between 0 in 1945 and the district's 1968 fraction of orchard area devoted to kiwifruit. Production before 1945 was negligible and assumed to be zero. The fraction of a district's orchard area devoted to kiwifruit in 1968, a key data point for these models, was obtained by "raking" from the marginal totals for fruits and districts.

For all districts apart from Taranaki, Westland and Southland, the model for kiwifruit orchard area (1945—1967) was formed in two steps. In step one a fraction of district orchard area p_t , $t = 1945, \dots, 1968$ was found by linear interpolation between 0% in 1907 and the district's 1968 proportion of area devoted to kiwifruit (5.9% in Auckland, 0.2% in Hawke's Bay, 1.5% in

Gisborne, 0.2% in Wellington, 0.2% in Marlborough, 0.3% in Nelson, 0.2% in Canterbury and 0.1% in Otago). This was used to find the yearly kiwifruit area for the district as $p_t A_t$, $t = 1945, \dots, 1968$ where A_t , $t = 1945, \dots, 1968$ is the district's total orchard area.

For Taranaki, Westland and Southland, kiwifruit orchard area in 1945—1967 was assumed to be zero since 0% of the district's orchard area was devoted to kiwifruit.

Fig. S4 shows the reconstructed time series for kiwifruit orchard area by district.

North Island orchard area fraction

Fig. S5 shows the yearly fraction of orchard area on the North Island for apples and kiwifruit.

The North Island consists of our five standardized districts (Auckland, Hawke's Bay, Gisborne (from 1923), Taranaki, and Wellington). Our district Auckland includes the regions historically known under a variety of names ("Auckland", "North Auckland", "Central Auckland", "South Auckland" and "Bay of Plenty").

Figure S4. Reconstructed time series for kiwifruit orchard area by district. (Figure continues on the next three pages).

Figure S4 continued. (Figure continues on the next two pages).

Figure S4 continued. (Figure continues on the next page).

Figure S4 continued.

Figure S5. The yearly fraction of orchard area on the North Island for apples (red) and kiwifruit (green).

Production data

Complete time series for apple and kiwifruit production volumes were created in two steps. First, complete time series of apple and kiwifruit yields were created. Second, these were combined with apple and kiwifruit orchard area to fill any gaps in the production time series. Yearly production in each district was modelled using the district's proportion of orchard area within the national total for that fruit.

Apple yields were used as stated, or calculated using national production volumes and apple orchard area when those were known and stated yields were not available. For 1902–1924 no yield or production data were available and 1902 yield was assumed to be half 1924 yield. Stineman interpolation was used for missing values of apple yield. Apple yield increased roughly by a factor of 25 from about 2.6 tonnes/ha in 1924 to 65 tonnes/ha in 2020.

Modelling kiwifruit production was more complicated than for apples. Total production was available from Official Yearbooks for most years in 1956–1981 (with gaps), and in 1988 and 1990. Data for subsequent years shifted to reporting exports rather than domestic production. We would have preferred to estimate yields using our model of kiwifruit orchard area, and interpolate using yields and orchard area. However, this creates some impossibly small production volumes. A necessary condition is that the total production volume must be at least the volume of exports (assuming carryover of fruit from one year to the next is small). We found this approach was insufficient. A possible reason for this may be in the difference between *planted* orchard area, which we modelled from Statistics NZ data, and *harvestable* orchard area which actually produces fruit in a year. It takes approximately five years for planted kiwifruit to enter production. In times when orchard area is increasing quickly, harvestable area will lag planted area, which we approximated by five years. This imposed a loose condition: the harvestable area could not be larger than the minimum planted area of the previous 5 years. We defined a “growth factor” as kiwifruit orchard area in the current year divided by the minimum kiwifruit orchard area of the previous five years. Where the ratio was greater than 1.2 we said the orchard area was experiencing high growth, and this occurred in two periods (1951–1960 and 1966–1988), as well as 2018–2020 (discussed below). In these two periods we calculated yields using the minimum of the kiwifruit orchard area in the previous five years as a proxy for harvestable area. These created sufficient production volumes to supply historical exports.

Kiwifruit data from 1991 onward has a focus on exports, which is less than the full domestic production. Data are particular to the reporting group (New Zealand Kiwifruit Marketing Board (NZKMB), later Zespri), for which kiwifruit orchard areas differ from Statistics NZ planted areas.

For this analysis, the data were adapted to create yield numbers compatible with our kiwifruit orchard areas, in a couple of steps. Production volume V_t in year t was known from NZ Statistics to 1981 (with gaps), and in 1988 and 1990. NZ kiwifruit orchard area A_t in year t was known from NZ Statistics or interpolated as described above. Yield $Y_t = V_t/A_t$ in year t could be calculated when the values were known. In particular, a 1990 base yield $Y_{1990} = V_{1990}/A_{1990}$ could be calculated. NZKMB/Zespri data, including yield and production volume submitted for export, used a financial year that ends on March 31. Quarterly kiwifruit export volumes from Statistics NZ were used to estimate the fraction of the year's export volume that was exported in the second quarter of the year. This was used to estimate the fraction of NZKMB/Zespri production from just the second quarter of the year. By shifting this second quarter production, a time series of production v_t in year t for financial years was obtained. A nominal yield $x_t = v_t/a_t$ could be calculated, where a_t is given as the "producing area". A 1990 base nominal yield $x_{1990} = v_{1990}/a_{1990}$ could be calculated. These nominal yields need not be compatible with our kiwifruit orchard areas. To achieve a more compatible result, a "nominal yield factor" time series $\alpha_t = x_t/x_{1990}$ for years t in 1991–2017 was created. This captured the multiplicative change in yield from 1990 as a base year. We then modelled the yield $Y_t = \alpha_t A_t$ by applying the multiplicative factor, and production volume $V_t = Y_t A_t$, for years t in 1991–2017.

The years 2018–2020 were years of high growth, so yield was handled differently. The minimum orchard area in the previous five years $B_t = \min\{A_{t-1}, \dots, A_{t-5}\}$ was used instead. Similar to the approach above, a yield factor $\beta_{2017} = x_t/x_{2017}$ was calculated from the nominal yields, from which the yield was modelled as $U_t = \beta_t U_{2017}$ for years t in 2018–2020 and a 2017 base yield $U_{2017} = V_{2017}/B_{2017}$. Production was modelled as $V_t = \beta_t U_t$ for years t in 2018–2020.

Export data and packout rates

Complete yearly export data (total value and volume) were available for apples (1910–2020). Similar data for kiwifruit were less complete. Missing export volumes between 1952 (taken as the last year of zero exports) and 2020 were addressed using Stineman interpolation. The yearly total value of kiwifruit exports were unknown in 1953–1974. We approximated these values using the product of the 1975 export value per tonne and the yearly export volume, adjusted for inflation.

Complete yearly apple export data by country (total value and volume) was available for apples (1964–2020; code 0514) from the World Bank. The quality and coverage exceeded what we could find on the Statistics NZ website. By comparison with Statistics NZ data we inferred that “Taiwan” in Statistics NZ data is labelled “Other Asia, nes” in the World Bank data. Similarly, yearly kiwifruit export data by country (total value and volume) is available from the FAO (1990–1995; CPC code “01352”) and World Bank (1996–2020; code “081050”). By comparing the FAO data with other data sources (Statistics NZ, World Bank) we inferred the FAO data was missing the situation in which the export country is unspecified (basically exports to the European Union). We imputed these values each year as the difference between the Statistics NZ export total and the FAO export total. To maintain the primacy of Statistics NZ data, we used these datasets to create yearly distributions of export volume and value by country, which we applied to Statistics NZ totals.

Not all fruit that is produced achieves a quality that is suitable for export. The “packout rate” is the yearly fraction of fruit that is exportable. We used an estimated packout rate to more accurately capture a supply restriction in one of our scenarios. Using export volume and production volume time series, we estimated the packout rates for apples and kiwifruit separately as the fraction of production volume that was exported. Technically, this is the fraction of production that was *exported*, not *exportable*. But this approach has two key advantages. It necessarily creates an exportable production volume that agrees with the historic export volumes in the baseline situation. Our estimated packout rates showed high variability and a noticeable trend (Fig. S6), even if focussing on just the years with complete (i.e., not interpolated) export and production volume data. This speaks against using a single number for each fruit. Even a smooth trend would pose problems because the variability could have estimated exportable fruit volume smaller than the empirical exported fruit volume in a year. Our approach ensured this never happens.

Figure S6. Estimated packout rates for apples and kiwifruit.

Baseline and scenarios

The baseline against which we defined losses was the historical record as captured by our prepared data. We focused on the 1964–2020 period, for two reasons. We had the best trade data for this time. But, as we will show, even after adjusting for inflation, this period captures, by far, the most relevant period of trade.

To define our scenarios, we grouped export markets into four tiers and considered a “best case” and “worst case” version of each scenario. Tier 1 were countries/regions in which a market analysis for Western Australia market opportunities identified that New Zealand supplies apples at the high or premium end of the market (Radhakrishnan 2017 p. 50). We would expect to see higher unit prices. Lack of Western Australia apple exports may also indicate an aversion to exports from a region where medfly is established. Tiers 2 and 3 captured other countries where we believed trade may have been impacted based on their response to the 1996 medfly incursion or a biosecurity regimen known to be strict. Like Tier 1, Tier 2 were countries/regions where we believe trade would be impacted. With Tier 3 we were less certain about trade impacts, so we considered both possibilities on a best case/worst case basis. China is a large export market. By placing it in Tier 3, we considered the situations where there are and are not additional trade restrictions. Tier 4 includes all other countries/regions, for which we assume no trade impacts would have occurred.

In Scenario 1 we considered the case in which medfly has spread throughout New Zealand, so affects the North and South Islands equally. Table 1 (main article) summarizes the restrictions. In the best case, Tiers 1 and 2 are affected. In the worst case, Tiers 1, 2 and 3 are affected. Where a Tier is affected, we assume the fruit is redirected to other markets, and the unit price (i.e., dollars per tonne) for the fruit is the lesser of the unit price for that tier and Tier 4 (calculated yearly). Where the Tier 4 unit price is lower (the usual case), a loss is created. In Scenario 1 we do not model supply restrictions, only the loss of any premium pricing.

In Scenario 2 we considered the case in which medfly is established in the North Island only. We assumed South Island fruit can continue to supply restricted markets, but North Island fruit can only supply Tier 4 (more restrictive case) or Tiers 3 and 4 (less restrictive case). Exportable fruit was allocated to Tiers 1-4 in order, as available. Unlike Scenario 1, we used our model of exportable fruit to more closely model the amount of exportable supply available for the upper tiers. Similar to Scenario 1, North Island fruit (from a medfly area) was assumed to be redirected to Tier 4 and sell at the lesser of the unit price for that tier and Tier 4 (calculated yearly). Where the Tier 4 unit price was lower (the usual case), a loss was created.

The lack of early kiwifruit trade data limited our calculation of losses to 1990 and later. To cover the same period as apple losses (namely 1964–2020), we estimated kiwifruit losses in 1964–1989 by extrapolation. That is, we extrapolated the worst case losses as a fraction of export value, and the best case losses as a fraction of the worst case losses. This approach ensured best case losses cannot exceed worst case losses, and worst case losses cannot exceed the export value.

Extrapolation of Kiwifruit losses to 1964—1989: Scenario 1

For extrapolation of Scenario 1 worst case losses in the 1964-1989 period, three linear regression models were explored by fitting the losses from 1990-2020. Models were fit using the `lm()` command in R and evaluated using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) as an indication of model fit (smaller is better). The models were: Model 1, $y \sim x$ (BIC = 34.20); Model 2, $y \sim x + \text{Year}$ (BIC = 37.61); Model 3, $y \sim x + \text{Year} + \text{Year}^2$, (BIC = 38.02) where x is log of kiwifruit export value and y is log of Scenario 1 worst case losses (Fig. S7).

An extrapolation model for Scenario 1 best case losses was found by fitting a logistic-regression (specifically a “quasibinomial”) model in R for best case losses as a fraction of worst case losses over the early period 1990-2000. Data after 2000 are noisy and show trends unrelated to the pre-2000 period. The models were: Model A, $y \sim 1$; Model B, $y \sim \text{Year}$; Model C, $y \sim \text{Year} + \text{Year}^2$ (Fig. S8). Models B and C were highly influenced by the data point for 1990.

Extrapolation of Kiwifruit losses to 1964—1989: Scenario 2

For extrapolation of Scenario 2 worst case losses in the 1964-1989 period, three linear regression models were explored by fitting the losses from 1990-2020. Models were fit using the `lm()` command in R and evaluated using the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) as an indication of model fit (smaller is better). The models were: Model 1, $y \sim x$ (BIC = 32.83); Model 2, $y \sim x + \text{Year}$ (BIC = 36.16); Model 3, $y \sim x + \text{Year} + \text{Year}^2$, (BIC = 38.05) where x is log of kiwifruit export value and y is log of Scenario 2 worst case losses (Fig. S9).

An extrapolation model for Scenario 2 best case losses was found by fitting a logistic-regression (specifically a “quasibinomial”) model in R for best case losses as a fraction of worst case losses over the early period 1990-2000. Data after 2000 are noisy and show trends unrelated to the pre-2000 period. The models were: Model A, $y \sim 1$; Model B, $y \sim \text{Year}$; Model C, $y \sim \text{Year} + \text{Year}^2$ (Fig. S10). Models B and C were highly influenced by the data point for 1990.

Figure S7. Value of kiwifruit exports (black) and scenario 1 worst case losses (red) with regression models 1 (blue), 2 (green) and 3 (orange).

Figure S8. Scenario 1 best case losses (black) with logistic regression model A (blue), B (green) and C (orange). Models were fitted on the period 1990-2020.

Figure S9. Value of kiwifruit exports (black) and scenario 2 worst case losses (red) with regression models 1 (blue), 2 (green) and 3 (orange).

Figure S10. Scenario 2 best case losses (black) with logistic regression model A (blue), B (green) and C (orange). Models are fit on the period 1990-2020.

Wider economic impacts

In addition to direct benefits of fruit fly freedom, we also considered the larger economic impacts, including additional flow-on benefits. Our estimate of economic impact was based on an economic multiplier calculated from economic model data from Underwood (2007) (Table S3). We used a multiplier capturing the total losses as a proportion of direct losses: $(92.38 + 105.28) / 92.38 = 2.14$. That study considers the effect of a medfly incursion in each of three areas (Bay of Plenty, Hawke's Bay, and the Nelson/Tasman region) which together comprise the majority of fresh fruit production in New Zealand.

Table S3. Direct revenue and flow-on losses in Underwood (2007, p. 64–66) from hypothetical medfly incursions, used to calculate an economic multiplier to estimate economic impact.

Region	Direct revenue losses (\$ million)	Flow-on losses (\$ million)
Bay of Plenty	47.54	51.78
Hawke's Bay	35.96	42.51
Nelson & Tasman	8.88	10.95
Total	92.38	105.24

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